

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Zid**FIRST NAME:** Salim**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the purpose of using quotation marks when citing a direct quotation in academic writing, and how are long quotations typically formatted?
 - Quotation marks are used to highlight the author's name and the page number for proper citation, and long quotations are formatted with double quotation marks (""") to distinguish them from shorter quotes.
 - Quotation marks are used to emphasize the importance of the author's words, and long quotations are formatted by indenting them without quotation marks.
 - Quotation marks are used to indicate that the information is taken directly from the source, and long quotations are formatted without any indentation or special formatting.

- Quotation marks are used to set off the author’s words from the rest of the text and to signal the start and end of a direct quotation, and long quotations are formatted with no quotation marks and an indentation.¹**
2. Why are style guides important in various types of writing, and what is their primary purpose?
- Style guides are crucial for achieving coherence and consistency in writing, especially when multiple authors contribute, and they help ensure that the finished publication reflects the style of the publication, company, or website rather than individual writers.²**
- Style guides are essential to enforce the personal writing style of individual authors and make each piece unique within a publication, company, or website.
- Style guides help maintain consistency in writing style across different authors and ensure that the final publication reflects the personal style of the individual writer.
- Style guides are primarily associated with creative writing and are not relevant to technical writing, commercial writing, journalism, or web copywriting.
3. What are the common pitfalls to avoid when writing early drafts for research papers, and why is it important not to fall into these traps?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021),34–35.

² Ibid., 41.

- Writing an early draft for a research paper often involves creating a narrative of discovery, compiling various source quotations, and mirroring the assignment structure. Falling into these traps is a normal part of the writing process and does not hinder the development of original ideas or engagement with readers.
- ☑ **The common pitfalls to avoid when writing early drafts for research papers include creating a narrative of discovery, relying heavily on source quotations, and mirroring the assignment structure. Avoiding these pitfalls is essential because they can hinder the development of original ideas and fail to engage readers effectively.³**
- The main purpose of early writing in research is to communicate ideas directly to readers, even if it means following a narrative of discovery, relying heavily on source quotations, or mirroring the assignment structure. These approaches can be effective in conveying research findings.
- The common pitfalls when writing early drafts for research papers include providing excessive detail, using complex language, and focusing too much on your own ideas. Avoiding these pitfalls is essential because they can make the writing confusing and inaccessible to readers.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 68.

4. When should the first letter of each element in the names of specific people, places, and organizations be capitalized according to common style guidelines, and what exceptions might apply?
- In academic writing, all names, including those of people, places, and organizations, should have the first letter of each element capitalized consistently, regardless of particles or compound last names.
 - The first letter of each element in the names of specific people, places, and organizations should be capitalized except for personal names containing particles or compound last names. In these cases, capitalization may vary.⁴**
 - Capitalization rules for names in academic writing depend on the writer's preference and can vary widely. It's advisable to follow the Chicago Manual of Style for guidance in all cases.
 - Names of people, places, and organizations should always be presented in italics, and capitalization rules are not a significant concern in academic writing.
5. What are the types of abbreviations, and when should abbreviations be used in academic writing?
- The types of abbreviations include acronyms, initialisms, and contractions. Abbreviations should be used extensively in academic writing to maintain formality and clarity.

⁴ Ibid., 328–329.

- The course discusses three types of abbreviations: acronyms, initialisms, and contractions. In academic writing, abbreviations should be used liberally to enhance the readability of the text.
 - The course mentions two types of abbreviations: acronyms and initialisms. Abbreviations should be used sparingly in academic writing, primarily for frequently used names, titles, and terms.⁵**
 - The text identifies four types of abbreviations: acronyms, initialisms, contractions, and anagrams. Academic writing should avoid the use of abbreviations altogether to ensure clarity and formality.
6. What role does the philosophy of science play in the methodology section of a research study, and why is it crucial to ensure alignment between the chosen research methods and the underlying philosophy of science?
- The philosophy of science is irrelevant in the methodology section of a research study, as it primarily focuses on practical methods and data collection. Alignment between research methods and philosophy is not necessary.
 - The philosophy of science informs the choice of research methods and helps guide the selection of appropriate methods for a study. Ensuring alignment between methodology and methods enhances the credibility and validity of the research.⁶**

⁵ Ibid., 353.

⁶ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee-Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 34.

- The philosophy of science is the sole focus of the methodology section and does not affect the choice of research methods. Research methods can be selected independently of the underlying philosophy.
 - The philosophy of science plays a minor role in the methodology section, primarily related to the historical context of the research. Ensuring alignment between methodology and methods is optional and does not significantly impact the research quality.
7. In research methodology, what is the purpose of including a treatment or intervention section in a study, and how does its title vary between quantitative experimental and qualitative research designs?
- The treatment or intervention section is included to describe the experiences of participants in different groups and their exposure to specific techniques and resources that aim to impact research variables. In quantitative experimental research, this section is titled "Intervention," whereas in qualitative research, it is titled "Treatment."⁷**
 - The treatment or intervention section is not necessary in research methodology, as it does not provide valuable insights into the research design. Its title remains the same regardless of whether the study is quantitative experimental or qualitative.
 - The treatment or intervention section serves to provide a detailed account of the study's objectives and is essential in both quantitative experimental and qualitative

⁷ Ibid., 44.

- research. The title varies based on the research focus, with "Treatment" used in quantitative and "Intervention" in qualitative research.
- The treatment or intervention section is primarily concerned with statistical analysis and is only relevant to quantitative experimental research. Its title is "Treatment" in both types of research, regardless of the research design.
8. What are the key components and considerations when presenting findings in the findings chapter of a dissertation, and why is it important to include these elements?
- The findings chapter primarily serves to restate research questions and hypotheses, with no need for additional explanations. Simple analyses are presented in tables, while complex ones are discussed in the text. Including effect sizes for inferential statistics is optional.
 - In the findings chapter, it is essential to restate research questions and hypotheses and present the results of complex analyses in tables and figures. Reporting internal consistency and inter-rater reliability is unnecessary, as it doesn't contribute to the reader's understanding of the findings.
 - The findings chapter should begin with a description of its organization, restate research questions and hypotheses, and present the results using tables and figures for complex analyses. Effect sizes for inferential statistics should be reported, along with internal consistency and inter-rater reliability to establish the practical significance of the findings.⁸**

⁸ Ibid., 54.

- The findings chapter focuses solely on presenting raw data in a qualitative study and doesn't require a description of organization, restating research questions, or reporting statistical analyses. Effect sizes, internal consistency, and inter-rater reliability are not applicable to qualitative research.
9. What is the primary purpose of the discussion chapter in a dissertation, and how does it integrate the findings with the literature reviewed?
- The primary purpose of the discussion chapter is to summarize the findings of the dissertation without considering their implications for theory, research, practice, education, or policy. The chapter does not need to reference the literature reviewed.
 - The discussion chapter serves as a space to restate the research questions and hypotheses without linking them to the findings. It does not need to refer to the literature reviewed, as this is unrelated to the dissertation's purpose.
 - The discussion chapter aims to provide an interpretation of the dissertation findings within the context of the literature reviewed. It uses key citations to support this interpretation and may suggest alternate explanations based on the researcher's understanding of the field.⁹**
 - The discussion chapter primarily serves as a reflection on the research process and does not involve integrating the findings with the literature reviewed. Its main focus is on the personal experiences of the doctoral student during the research journey.

⁹ Ibid., 57.

10. What are the guidelines for formatting personal names and titles in running text, and how does English style differ from non-English practices?

- In running text, personal surnames should always be capitalized, with the first name abbreviated to its initial. English style follows the same practice as non-English languages for personal names and titles.
- Personal surnames should be uppercased in running text to highlight them, while the first name should be spelled out the first time and abbreviated thereafter. This practice differs from non-English languages, which use initials for first names.¹⁰**
- Personal names should retain their original accents, and the German character "ß" should be replaced with "ss." In English, personal names and titles should not include accents or special characters.
- When addressing individuals, it is courteous to use "Ms" in English, regardless of marital status, unless the person prefers a different title. In non-English languages like French and German, "Mme" and "Frau" are equivalent to "Mrs" and denote marital status.

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¹⁰ European Union, *English Style Guide-A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Union, 2021), 39.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.